

ISic1408

I.Sicily inscription 1408

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone (local)

Object

column capital

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

30.09.13

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Megara Hyblaea

Place of origin (modern)

Megara Iblea

Provenance

West necropolis

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 1

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140917

1. Καλισ.εος {²⁷Καλίσ[τ]εος} □ εἰμί.

2.

Edition: PHI330079

1. Καλιστέο̄ς ²⁶Καλλιστέως²⁶ □ εἰμί.

2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 493025

EDCS 39101537

PHI 140917

PHI 330079

Bibliography

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